

**INNOVATION AND INQUISITIVENESS AS DRIVERS OF
COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN PRIVATE HOSPITALS: EVIDENCE
FROM DELTA STATE, NIGERIA**

By

FRANCIS I. OGOSI AND OBIRE KENNEDY OGHENESUVWE

**Department of Business Administration, Western Delta University, Oghara, Delta State
Nigeria**

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

FRANCIS I. OGOSI PhD

Department of Business Administration
Western Delta University, Oghara, Nigeria

Email : francis.ogosi@wdu.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3892-4175

ABSTRACT

In the face of escalating competition and resource constraints, private hospitals in emerging economies like Nigeria must leverage internal capabilities to remain competitive. This study explores the role of innovation and inquisitiveness as drivers of competitive advantage in private hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria. Innovation, encompassing technological, administrative, and clinical advancements, enables hospitals to differentiate themselves and improve service delivery. Inquisitiveness, defined as the organizational tendency to seek new knowledge and challenge existing practices, fosters a culture of learning and adaptability. Using data from 80 senior management personnel across 16 private hospitals, the study examines how these two capabilities influence competitive advantage, operationalized as service differentiation, patient responsiveness, and market adaptability. Results from multiple regression analysis indicate that innovation has a significant positive impact on competitive advantage ($\beta = 0.278$, $p = 0.007$), while inquisitiveness, although positively related, does not significantly affect competitive advantage ($\beta = 0.154$, $p = 0.113$). The findings suggest that while innovation contributes to long-term competitiveness, inquisitiveness alone is insufficient without supporting systems. The study concludes by recommending that private hospitals prioritize innovation as a strategic capability, while fostering an environment where inquisitiveness can be institutionalized to support continuous improvement.

Keywords: Innovation, Inquisitiveness, Competitive Advantage, Healthcare Management, Dynamic Capabilities

JEL Classification: I11; L25; M10; O32

INTRODUCTION

In today's complex and fast-evolving healthcare environment, organizations are increasingly compelled to develop internal capabilities that allow them to anticipate, respond to, and thrive amidst dynamic changes. These changes stem from multiple drivers, including technological advancement, growing patient awareness, demographic transitions, economic constraints, and policy instability (Teece, 2007; Damanpour & Aravind, 2012). In emerging economies like Nigeria, the healthcare sector is characterized by resource shortages, uneven access, infrastructural gaps, and service delivery inefficiencies. As public healthcare continues to face these persistent challenges, private hospitals are under pressure to play a compensatory role. To do so effectively and competitively, they must improve on not only physical infrastructure and medical equipment but also intangible strategic capabilities that support adaptability, learning, and innovation (Barney, 1991; World Bank, 2022).

One of such capability is innovation, defined as the intentional introduction and application of new ideas, processes, products, or procedures that are designed to significantly benefit individuals, teams, organizations, or society (Crossan & Apaydin, 2010). As opined by Topol, (2022), in healthcare, innovation manifests in clinical technologies, digital platforms, treatment protocols, operational models, and patient engagement strategies, while Lee & Lee, (2022), averred that innovative private hospitals are able to deliver higher-quality care, streamline their operations, differentiate themselves in a competitive marketplace, and respond effectively to patient demands. In the Nigerian context, where hospitals operate under financial, infrastructural, and regulatory constraints, innovation has the potential to yield high strategic returns by driving service differentiation and operational efficiency (Oyedele & Akintunde, 2020; Akanji & Ayodele, 2022).

However, the capacity to innovate does not emerge in isolation; it is often nurtured within an environment that encourages learning, curiosity, and continuous improvement. This introduces the concept of inquisitiveness, an often overlooked but critical organizational trait. Inquisitiveness refers to the tendency of individuals and institutions to seek new knowledge, explore unknown areas, question existing routines, and remain intellectually open (Loewenstein, 1994; Kashdan & Ciarrochi, 2013). In inquisitive healthcare organizations, frontline workers and administrators actively engage in reflective learning, performance reviews, and solution-seeking behaviors, which foster a culture of experimentation and growth (Kumar et al., 2022; Hughes et al., 2018). These characteristics are aligned with the "sensing" function in the Dynamic Capabilities Theory, which is crucial for identifying opportunities and threats in a rapidly evolving environment (Teece et al., 1997).

Despite their relevance, both innovation and inquisitiveness remain underdeveloped in many Nigerian private hospitals, particularly in states outside the major economic hubs. The majority of healthcare organisations continue to function with strict hierarchies, little staff empowerment, inadequate feedback systems, and little investment in digital infrastructure (Ameh et al., 2021). In Delta State; a strategic yet under-researched region in southern Nigeria, private hospitals face unique challenges such as inadequate public health coordination, weak training mechanisms, and infrastructural deficits in the face increasing competition and patient demands. Yet, there is little

empirical evidence on how internal capabilities like innovation and inquisitiveness are mobilized to create competitive advantage within this context.

This study therefore investigated the influence of innovation and inquisitiveness on the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria. By focusing on these two dimensions of adaptive capability, the study intends to contribute to ongoing debates in strategic healthcare management on about how organizations in resource-constrained environments build resilience and outperform their peers. It also fills a notable empirical and geographical gap in the literature by exploring the dynamics of capability-based competitiveness in a semi-urban Nigerian healthcare context. The findings are expected to offer practical implications for hospital administrators, policymakers, and healthcare investors committed to strengthening the private health sector in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Problem Statement

While innovation and inquisitiveness have been widely theorized as essential drivers of organizational competitiveness, their practical influence within the healthcare systems of developing regions—particularly at the subnational level—remains poorly understood. Most empirical studies in Nigeria have concentrated on innovation alone, often overlooking inquisitiveness as a distinct strategic capability. Additionally, the majority of research has focused on large urban centers or corporate sectors, leaving private hospitals in transitional and semi-urban regions like Delta State significantly under-researched. Without contextual insights into how these adaptive capabilities function in real healthcare settings, administrators may struggle to design effective strategies for achieving and sustaining competitive advantage. This study addresses this gap by examining how innovation and inquisitiveness individually and jointly affect competitive outcomes in private hospitals operating in Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The overall objective of this study is to examine the effect of innovation and inquisitiveness on the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the effect of innovation on competitive advantage in private hospitals.
2. Examine the effect of inquisitiveness on competitive advantage in private hospitals.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does innovation influence the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State?
2. How does inquisitiveness affect the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested in the course of this study:

H₀₁: Innovation has no significant effect on the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State.

H₀₂: Inquisitiveness has no significant effect on the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State.

Scope and Justification of the Study

This study was delimited to registered private hospitals located in key urban centers of Delta State, including Warri, Asaba, Ughelli, and Sapele. It focuses exclusively on senior management personnel, such as medical directors, administrators, department heads, and lead consultants—who are responsible for driving innovation, policy execution, and performance evaluation within their institutions. This managerial focus is justified by the strategic nature of the constructs under investigation, which require decision-making authority and long-term organizational insight. The justification for choosing Delta State stems from its underrepresentation in scholarly literature despite being a vital commercial and healthcare hub in southern Nigeria. By examining internal capabilities in this unique context, the study provides context-specific evidence that can inform healthcare strategy in similar resource-constrained environments. The findings are expected to be beneficial to hospital managers, healthcare consultants, policymakers, and scholars interested in the intersection of strategic capability and health service competitiveness in low- and middle-income countries.

CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE

Innovation

Innovation refers to the introduction and implementation of new ideas, processes, services, or technologies aimed at improving organizational performance or creating competitive value. In the healthcare sector, innovation can be technological (e.g., adopting telemedicine or electronic health records), administrative (e.g., restructuring service delivery workflows), or clinical (e.g., introducing new treatment protocols). According to Crossan and Apaydin (2010), innovation is a multidimensional construct that includes both the generation of novel ideas and their effective application. In private hospitals, innovation enhances operational efficiency, improves patient outcomes, and facilitates responsiveness to market and regulatory changes.

Healthcare organizations that actively innovate are more likely to develop strategic advantages by offering superior quality, reducing cost-to-service ratios, and introducing differentiated patient experiences (Topol, 2022; Lee & Lee, 2022). For instance, the use of automated diagnostics and remote consultation platforms can not only improve patient satisfaction but also extend access to underserved areas. In the Nigerian context, where public hospitals often suffer from outdated infrastructure and bureaucratic inefficiencies, innovation becomes a strategic tool

for private hospitals seeking to attract clients who value speed, quality, and modern care (Eze et al., 2019; Oyedele & Akintunde, 2020).

However, innovation in resource-constrained environments faces significant barriers. These include limited access to capital, resistance to change, lack of skilled personnel, and regulatory rigidity. Despite these constraints, even small-scale, incremental innovations such as mobile-based appointment scheduling, solar-powered backup systems, or simplified patient triage protocols, can generate considerable competitive gains. Akanji and Ayodele (2022) highlighted that Nigerian hospitals that adopt routine service innovations, even without major technological shifts, perform better in terms of patient retention and operational sustainability.

Innovation is thus conceptualized as a component of adaptive capability—that is, an internal organizational strength that enables the hospital to identify and implement new ideas in ways that create strategic advantage. The ability to create, implement, and institutionalise new procedures that meet patient expectations and market demands is more important than merely having cutting-edge tools or technology. This is consistent with the Resource-Based View (RBV), which views innovation as a rare, valuable, and unique resource that can provide long-term competitive advantage.

Inquisitiveness

The cognitive and cultural inclination of an organisation or its members towards learning, curiosity, and the pursuit of novel information or alternate solutions is known as inquisitiveness. It is a proactive quality that promotes inquiry, openness to criticism, exploration, and ongoing development (Loewenstein, 1994; Kashdan & Ciarrochi, 2013). In the healthcare industry, curiosity promotes adaptability by creating settings where experts challenge long-standing practices, suggest fresh ideas, and keep up with developments in clinical or operational science. Curiosity serves as a catalyst for learning, innovation, and strategic renewal when it is ingrained in company culture.

According to Kumar et al., (2022); and Hughes et al., (2018), curious workers are more likely to collaborate across functional boundaries, critically evaluate patient feedback, and recommend enhancements to service workflows. Mechanisms such as brainstorming sessions, after-action reviews, open-door policies, and multidisciplinary learning platforms are frequently promoted by inquisitive organisations. In addition to increasing employee engagement, these structures foster institutional agility, which is essential for handling healthcare crises and uncertainties. Being inquisitive guarantees that organisations stay vigilant and responsive in the face of changing patient preferences, regulatory changes, and technological disruption.

However, in Nigerian hospital settings, where open inquiry is hindered by traditional authority structures, a lack of performance feedback, and fear of criticism, inquisitiveness is not always innate (Ali et al., 2020; Saidu et al., 2021). In these situations, it is necessary to intentionally foster curiosity through cultural reinforcement, structured training, and leadership modelling. Furthermore, a psychologically safe workplace where staff members feel free to voice concerns, make suggestions, and ask questions without worrying about repercussions is necessary for inquisitiveness. In the absence of these prerequisites, curiosity might continue to be a latent quality with minimal discernible impact on organisational results.

Inquisitiveness is thus an organisational capability—a collective, systemic quality that helps private hospitals recognise and react to change—rather than just an individual personality trait.

The concept aligns with the "sensing" function in the Dynamic Capabilities Theory, which highlights the importance of scanning and interpreting the environment as a precursor to adaptation. While inquisitiveness may not always yield immediate performance improvements, it lays the foundation for long-term competitiveness by enabling strategic foresight, knowledge acquisition, and reflective learning.

Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantage refers to the ability of an organization to outperform its rivals by offering superior value, achieving operational excellence, or sustaining customer loyalty over time. Porter (1985) defined it as a position of superiority that enables an organization to deliver products or services either at lower cost or with unique benefits that justify premium pricing. In the healthcare sector, competitive advantage may be realized through better patient outcomes, shorter waiting times, technological superiority, or exceptional customer service. It is not merely about short-term financial performance, but about creating lasting distinctiveness that patients, regulators, and partners recognize as valuable as indicated by Barney, (1991); and Lee & Lee, (2022).

In private hospitals, competitive advantage is typically driven by internal resources such as skilled personnel, clinical technology, brand reputation, and strategic capabilities like innovation and adaptability. Hospitals that could attract and retain top talent, introduce new diagnostic methods, or personalize patient care often achieve market differentiation and improved client satisfaction. Oyedele and Akintunde (2020) emphasized that Nigerian private hospitals that innovate consistently and respond quickly to patient feedback tend to dominate their local markets. In settings like Delta State, where public health services are frequently overburdened or under-resourced, competitive advantage becomes even more important as a survival mechanism. The Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) provide strong theoretical grounding for understanding competitive advantage in healthcare organizations. The RBV posits that sustainable competitive advantage arises from internal resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (Barney, 1991). When innovation and curiosity are ingrained in routines and culture, they become such intangible assets. Conversely, DCT concentrates on how businesses combine, develop, and reorganise internal and external capabilities to deal with quickly evolving contexts (Teece et al., 1997). This viewpoint is particularly pertinent to the healthcare industry, where strategic adaptability is necessary due to patient demands, technological advancements, and public health emergencies.

The outcome variable arising from an organization's internal adaptive capabilities, specifically innovation and inquisitiveness, is conceptualised as competitive advantage. It includes a hospital's capacity to maintain a strong market position, provide consistently high-quality services, and effectively handle environmental volatility. Profitability is not the only metric used to evaluate competitive advantage; other performance metrics like patient satisfaction, service accessibility, process efficiency, and organisational reputation are also considered. The fundamental premise is that private hospitals with strong adaptive qualities will be better equipped to compete in the fiercely competitive and increasingly customer-focused healthcare industry.

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

The Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT), are two well-known organisational theories that describe the strategic underpinnings of performance and adaptability in competitive environments, serve as the foundation for this investigation. These frameworks are suitable as they highlight how internal organisational characteristics, such as innovation and inquisitiveness, shape long-term competitiveness, particularly in dynamic and resource-constrained environments like the healthcare industry in Nigeria.

Resource-Based View (RBV)

According to the Resource-Based View, which was initially presented by Barney (1991), firms can gain a sustained competitive edge by utilising internal resources that are valuable, rare, unique, and non-replaceable or valuable, rare, inimitable, non-substitutable (a.k.a. VRIN attributes). According to this perspective, the firm's ability to succeed is determined by its particular resource configuration rather than the external environment. These resources can be either intangible (like organisational culture, innovation potential, or employee knowledge) or tangible (like infrastructure, medical technology). According to the RBV, companies need to recognise, develop, and safeguard these essential assets in order to keep a competitive advantage. RBV emphasises innovation and inquisitiveness as intangible strategic assets in the context of private hospitals. When innovation is ingrained in company procedures, safeguarded by internal culture, and challenging for rivals to imitate, it is considered a VRIN resource. In a similar vein, hospitals can produce insights, predict patient needs, and adjust faster than competitors when curiosity is fostered across teams and systems. By converting learning into service enhancements, these organisations can attain operational distinctiveness. Despite operating in the same geographic or regulatory environment, some hospitals routinely perform better than others, and the RBV offers a helpful lens through which to view this phenomenon.

RBV supports the objectives of this study, which evaluated the impact of internal capabilities on hospital performance, by concentrating on the internal sources of competitive advantage. A hospital's capacity to rely on its own strengths is even more important in healthcare settings where external factors, such as infrastructure or policy, are unpredictable or unstable. Therefore, RBV explains why adaptable qualities like innovation and inquisitiveness are not only helpful tools but also strategic requirements for hospitals looking to thrive in Nigeria's healthcare system.

Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT)

By concentrating on how businesses modify their resource base in reaction to changes in the environment, Teece, Pisano, and Shuen's (1997) Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) expands and builds upon the RBV. DCT places more emphasis on how businesses develop, integrate, and reorganize resources to stay in line with changing operational and market demands than RBV does on having strategic resources. In unstable sectors like healthcare, where adaptability, learning, and responsiveness are essential for sustained competitiveness, this theory is especially pertinent.

Three fundamental aspects of dynamic capabilities are identified by DCT: reconfiguration, seizing, and sensing. Sensing entails scanning the internal and external environment for opportunities and threats; seizing entails deploying resources to take advantage of those opportunities; and reconfiguring entails changing current systems or structures to conform to new realities. Since it reflects the organization's propensity to challenge accepted practices, solicit input, and investigate novel information, inquisitiveness is consistent with the "sensing" function in this study. Contrarily, innovation is associated with "seizing" and "reconfiguring," as it entails implementing new ideas and altering procedures in reaction to opportunities that are recognized.

DCT thus offers a useful framework for comprehending how businesses endure and prosper in the face of uncertainty, underfunding, and regulatory ambiguity in the context of private hospitals in Nigeria. Strong dynamic capabilities put hospitals in a better position to respond to technological disruption, public health emergencies, and changes in policy. This study adds to a growing body of research that sees healthcare competitiveness as dependent on strategic adaptability rather than stability by conceptualizing innovation and inquisitiveness as elements of dynamic capability. Therefore, DCT enhances RBV by elucidating not only the importance of resources but also how they are constantly mobilized and modified to remain relevant.

EMPIRICAL PERSPECTIVE

In "Innovation and Performance in Healthcare: Evidence from Nigerian Private Hospitals," Akanji and Ayodele (2022) used data from 132 private hospitals in Ogun State to examine the connection between innovation practices and hospital performance. The study utilized a structured questionnaire and regression analysis and found that both process and technological innovations were significantly related to higher patient satisfaction and operational efficiency. Similarly, Kumar et al. (2022) explored the effect of inquisitiveness on employee innovation in Indian healthcare settings, using structural equation modeling on data from 400 medical staff. They reported that inquisitiveness positively influenced creativity, which in turn impacted service quality. In another study, Oyedele and Akintunde (2020) examined the link between innovation and hospital competitiveness among 150 hospital administrators in Lagos State. They reported a strong positive relationship between innovative capacity (measured by adoption of ICT tools and new service formats) and competitive advantage. Saidu et al. (2021) studied inquisitiveness and adaptability in Abuja's private hospitals and found that inquisitiveness influenced competitiveness indirectly through employee engagement and organizational learning. Eze et al. (2019) also confirmed that hospitals in Southeast Nigeria with structured innovation programs outperformed their counterparts lacking such systems in terms of patient retention and financial viability.

Furthermore, Topol (2022) conducted a global review on digital innovation in healthcare and noted that organizations with strong innovation cultures adapted more quickly to COVID-19 disruptions, enhancing their competitive resilience. Ali et al. (2020) also examined inquisitiveness as a mediating variable between leadership style and organizational agility in 200 Pakistani hospitals, and indicated that inquisitiveness enhances responsiveness when supported by inclusive leadership. Duman and Akhtar (2022), in their systematic review of talent management in healthcare, identified inquisitiveness and innovation culture as key determinants

of employee retention and strategic agility. Nwokocha and Akinyemi (2021) examined 105 private hospitals in Port Harcourt and found that innovation capacity predicted 64% of the variance in service differentiation, a core proxy for competitiveness while Zubairu and Danjuma (2021) explored the role of innovation in sustaining SME competitiveness in Nigeria and concluded that firms with embedded innovation processes were more resilient, even in volatile environments. Collectively, these studies affirm that innovation and inquisitiveness, either independently or interactively, are essential predictors of strategic advantage, but few of them explore these constructs jointly within sub-national, healthcare-focused contexts such as Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional research design to examine the influence of innovation and inquisitiveness on competitive advantage among private hospitals in Delta State, Nigeria. Data were collected from all 80 senior management staff across 16 registered private hospitals using a structured questionnaire. A census sampling strategy was adopted due to the relatively small and accessible population, ensuring full coverage and minimizing sampling bias. The instrument was adapted from established scales in prior healthcare and organizational studies (e.g., Oyedele & Akintunde, 2020; Kumar et al., 2022). It comprised three constructs: innovation, inquisitiveness, and competitive advantage, each measured with six Likert-scale items (1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree). Items captured perceptions of innovation adoption, curiosity-driven practices, and service-based differentiation. Content validity was reviewed by subject matter experts, while a pilot test ensured clarity and internal consistency. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 24. Descriptive statistics summarized respondent perceptions, and multiple linear regression was employed to test the hypothesized relationships between the independent variables (innovation, inquisitiveness) and the dependent variable (competitive advantage). Statistical significance was assessed at $p < 0.05$. Multiple regression was preferred over separate simple regressions to evaluate the unique contribution of each predictor while accounting for their shared variance. This approach aligns with the study's theoretical underpinning in the Resource-Based View and Dynamic Capabilities Theory, which emphasize the interplay of internal capabilities in shaping competitive performance. The model also permits assessment of overall fit (R^2) and relative explanatory power across constructs.

FINDINGS

Findings from this study are presented in the table below;

Table 1: Regression Output Summary (Dependent Variable: Competitive Advantage)

Predictor	B	Std. Error	t	Sig. (p)	95% CI
Constant	1.771	0.401	4.41	.000	[0.972, 2.571]
Innovation	0.278	0.099	2.80	.007	[0.080, 0.476]
Inquisitiveness	0.154	0.097	1.59	.113	[-0.038, 0.346]

Model summary: $R^2 = 0.131$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.108$; $F(2, 77) = 5.818$, $p = 0.004$

Descriptive statistics revealed moderately high ratings across all constructs. Respondents rated their organizations relatively strong in innovation (Mean = 3.24, SD = 0.56), indicating moderate engagement with new ideas, technologies, and service redesign. Inquisitiveness also received fair agreement (Mean = 3.12, SD = 0.61), suggesting that while some curiosity and feedback-driven practices exist, they are not deeply institutionalized. Competitive advantage recorded the highest average score (Mean = 3.35, SD = 0.49), implying that most hospitals believe they enjoy a relatively strong position in terms of patient loyalty, service uniqueness, and reputation. These trends suggest that internal capabilities are present but may be under-leveraged in translating into long-term competitiveness.

DISCUSSION

Since this study was designed to assessing how both innovation and inquisitiveness influence competitive advantage, multiple linear regression was applied. This method allows for the simultaneous testing of multiple predictors, estimating the unique contribution of each while adjusting for shared variance. This is particularly important in organizational studies where strategic capabilities are interrelated. The model yielded an R^2 of 0.131, indicating that approximately 13.1% of the variance in competitive advantage is explained by the joint effect of innovation and inquisitiveness. The results from study were used to evaluate the hypothesis set out for this study.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Innovation has no significant effect on competitive advantage.

Regression results show that innovation has a statistically significant positive effect on competitive advantage ($\beta = 0.278$, $p = 0.007$). This means that as hospitals increase their capacity

to generate and implement new ideas, adopt digital tools, and refine service delivery processes, their competitive position improves. A unit increase in perceived innovation corresponds to a 0.278 unit increase in competitive advantage, holding inquisitiveness constant. This finding validates earlier studies (e.g., Oyedele & Akintunde, 2020; Nwokocha & Akinyemi, 2021) that link innovation to operational distinctiveness and market leadership in Nigerian private healthcare settings.

The result also reinforces the view that innovation functions as a VRIN (valuable, rare, inimitable, non-substitutable) resource under the Resource-Based View. It also supports the “seizing” and “reconfiguring” roles of innovation under Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece et al., 1997), where organizations transform internal knowledge into new service models. In Delta State, where infrastructural challenges persist, hospitals that embrace innovation—however incrementally gain strategic leverage in attracting and retaining patients. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected, confirming innovation as a significant predictor of competitive advantage.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Inquisitiveness has no significant effect on competitive advantage.

The regression output indicates that inquisitiveness, while positively associated with competitive advantage, does not exert a statistically significant influence ($\beta = 0.154$, $p = 0.113$). This suggests that curiosity-driven learning, while conceptually important, may not yield direct competitive returns unless supported by enabling systems, leadership, and institutional feedback structures. Although hospitals with inquisitive staff may generate new ideas or identify performance gaps, the absence of follow-through mechanisms may limit the translation of curiosity into performance gains.

This outcome highlights a nuance in the application of Dynamic Capabilities Theory: the presence of “sensing” (inquisitiveness) alone may be insufficient without strong “seizing” and “reconfiguring” functions. It also reflects structural realities in many Nigerian private hospitals, where inquisitive tendencies may be discouraged by hierarchical cultures or resource constraints. The finding aligns with studies such as Saidu et al. (2021) and Ali et al. (2020), which suggest that inquisitiveness needs complementary enablers to influence outcomes. Consequently, the hypothesis is not rejected, as inquisitiveness was not found to be a significant predictor of competitive advantage.

Business Policy Implications

The findings of this study underscore the strategic relevance of internal capabilities, particularly innovation as a policy priority for private hospital management in Nigeria. The significant impact of innovation on competitive advantage suggests that private healthcare providers must move beyond ad hoc improvement efforts and adopt formal innovation frameworks. Business policies should institutionalize innovation across departments, through practices such as periodic service audits, patient-centric redesigns, investment in health technology, and the creation of innovation task forces. Additionally, innovation must be embedded in HR policy through innovation-focused performance metrics, staff training in design thinking, and continuous improvement cycles. The non-significant effect of inquisitiveness also sends a critical signal to

policymakers: curiosity alone is insufficient without enabling systems. To harness inquisitiveness meaningfully, policies must prioritize psychological safety, inclusive leadership, and structured feedback mechanisms that convert ideas into implementable changes. Without such policy infrastructure, the adaptive capacity of the hospital remains untapped. In essence, innovation and inquisitiveness must be supported by governance structures that reward idea implementation and enable bottom-up improvement.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of innovation and inquisitiveness on the competitive advantage of private hospitals in Delta State. Results showed that innovation has a statistically significant positive effect on competitive advantage, confirming its role as a strategic asset that improves patient satisfaction, operational distinctiveness, and long-term positioning. Inquisitiveness, though positively related, was not found to significantly predict competitive advantage. These findings suggest that while private hospitals are beginning to embrace adaptive behaviors, the institutional systems required to fully leverage inquisitiveness may still be underdeveloped. Based on these insights, hospital administrators are encouraged to prioritize innovation as a central component of organizational strategy. This includes establishing permanent innovation committees, adopting agile project systems, and allocating dedicated innovation budgets. Additionally, though inquisitiveness may not yet yield measurable gains, it should be nurtured through a supportive culture that rewards questioning, encourages team learning, and protects staff from punitive responses to feedback or experimentation. Doing so would create the conditions necessary for inquisitiveness to evolve into a performance driver.

Suggestions for Further Research

Comparative studies across public and private hospitals can be carried out as it could offer further insights into how adaptive capabilities functions under different regulatory and structural conditions.

References

1. Akanji, T. O., & Ayodele, J. F. (2022). Innovation and performance in healthcare: Evidence from Nigerian private hospitals. *African Journal of Management Science*, 13(2), 45–58.
2. Ali, A., Malik, H., & Khan, R. (2020). Inquisitiveness and organizational agility: Mediating role of leadership style. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 13(4), 302–312.
3. Ameh, S., Abimbola, S., & Ozodiegwu, I. (2021). Health systems challenges in Nigeria: A focus on Delta State. *Nigerian Health Journal*, 21(1), 55–67.
4. Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639101700108>

5. Crossan, M. M., & Apaydin, M. (2010). A multi-dimensional framework of organizational innovation: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(6), 1154–1191.
6. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
7. Damanpour, F., & Aravind, D. (2012). Organizational structure and innovation revisited. In M. D. Mumford (Ed.), *Handbook of organizational creativity* (pp. 483–513). Academic Press.
8. Duman, M., & Akhtar, S. (2022). Talent management in healthcare: A systematic review. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 15(2), 155–165.
9. Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1–4.
10. Eze, C. I., Uche, O., & Ibe, C. (2019). Innovation and hospital competitiveness: Evidence from Southeast Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Health Economics*, 7(3), 88–99.
11. Hughes, D. J., Lee, A., Tian, A. W., Newman, A., & Legood, A. (2018). Leadership, creativity and innovation: A review and framework for future research. *Leadership Quarterly*, 29(5), 549–569.
12. Kashdan, T. B., & Ciarrochi, J. (2013). *Mindfulness, acceptance, and positive psychology: The seven foundations of well-being*. New Harbinger Publications.
13. Kashdan, T. B., Disabato, D. J., Goodman, F. R., McKnight, P. E., & Kelso, K. (2018). The curious advantage: How curiosity improves leadership outcomes. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 39(2), 139–155.
14. Kumar, R., Sharma, S., & Patel, A. (2022). Inquisitiveness and employee innovation: Evidence from Indian healthcare. *Journal of Organizational Behavior Studies*, 15(1), 99–113.
15. Lee, S. Y., & Lee, J. (2022). Quality of care and patient safety: A systematic review. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 34(1), 1–11.
16. Loewenstein, G. (1994). The psychology of curiosity: A review and reinterpretation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 116(1), 75–98.
17. Nwokocha, I., & Akinyemi, B. (2021). Innovation capacity and service differentiation in Nigerian clinics. *Journal of African Business Strategy*, 16(2), 64–79.
18. Oyedele, T., & Akintunde, R. (2020). Innovative potentials and hospital performance: A study of Lagos State. *Nigerian Journal of Business and Healthcare Innovation*, 9(4), 22–36.
19. Pallant, J. (2016). *SPSS survival manual* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
20. Porter, M. E. (1985). *Competitive advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance*. Free Press.
21. Saidu, Y., Mohammed, A., & Tanko, A. (2021). Inquisitiveness and competitiveness in Nigerian healthcare. *Journal of Organizational Studies in Africa*, 10(1), 55–67.
22. Teece, D. J. (2007). Explicating dynamic capabilities: The nature and microfoundations of sustainable enterprise performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319–1350.
23. Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509–533.

24. Topol, E. J. (2022). Adapting to the digital revolution in healthcare. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 386(10), 933–935. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp2117030>
25. World Bank. (2022). *Nigeria Health System Performance Profile*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/nigeria/publication>
26. World Health Organization. (2023). *Global Health Observatory: Health systems performance*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/data/gho>